

Clustering of TV shows using Machine Learning

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Abstract - Clustering is the grouping of specific objects based on their characteristics and similarities and it can be used in various fields. In the current scenario, where almost every work is being done online the use of OTT platforms for entertainment has recorded a significant increase. Thus we have taken two types of datasets of which one is on TV shows especially the ones available on an OTT platform like Netflix, Amazon Prime etc. We have performed data cleaning, removing missing values and preprocessing of the data using encoding techniques, normalization and visualization using various tools available. Apart from the main dataset we also took another dataset, in which we collected real data from users in the form of questionnaires about their favorite TV shows and have performed clustering on this dataset on the basis of age and no. of seasons of that show to understand where a person's interest is in terms of number of seasons and subsequently creating an age group of preferences. With all these results we can definitely give recommendations to people based on their interests and also predict the popularity of shows which will help us foresee the success of the shows.

Index Terms - TV SHOWS, CLUSTERING, OTT, AGGLOMERATIVE CLUSTERING, DBSCAN CLUSTERING.

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to the current pandemic situation, there has been a rise in the production of TV shows and movies to captivate the viewers with interesting plots,storylinesetc.Not to forget, the love for various TV shows of the last decades have made OTT big houses like Netflix, Prime Video, Disney+ etc to procure copyrights of these shows.

To begin with our process of using machine learning algorithms, we performed data cleaning, pre-processing the data ,also using encoding techniques according to the IMDb ratings, normalization of data and histograms, scatterplots etc are used for visualization of data. Further, we have implemented data mining i.e. two techniques of Clustering namely Hierarchical Clustering and DBSCAN Clustering to improvise and optimize the end results. We have created another dataset where the data is from real world users to combine results and procure better outcomes. Our venture here can help production companies in the decision making process so as to whether it is worthy to invest in a particular show since we can forecast the success and popularity of the show. Our work can also help viewers to find movies/TV shows according to their tastes and interests and provide them with separate other features like recommendations.

Some of our objectives are:

1. To determine the popularity of various TVshows based on the Ratings and the year the show was released.
2. To determine the interests of users based on their age group and no. of seasons a show contains.
3. To determine the maximum number of shows available on a particular OTT platform.
4. To provide recommendations of shows and movies using Ratings.
5. To forecast the success of TV shows based on Ratings.

A. Abbreviations and Acronyms

Table 1 Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	FULL FORM
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
OTT	Over The Top
IMDb	Internet Movie Database
AGNES	AGGLOMERATIVE CLUSTERING

DBSCAN	DENSITY BASE D SPAT IAL CLUSTERING WITH NOISE
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Table II presents detailed comparison of the clustering methods.

TABLE II: THE COMPARISON OF CLUSTERING METHODS

Type	Features	Characteristic	Algorithm
cluster	large amount of data can be processed	specify the number of clusters and methods	medoids
Density-based cluster	Any type of data	Reduce cluster quality and accuracy relatively	DBSCAN, OPTICS
Grid-based cluster	Fast scalable	Poor for high dimensional dataclustering	CLIQUE
Model-based cluster	Flexible and powerful	Limited to abnormal or high dimensional data	EM, COBWEB

II. DATASET

We have collected our dataset from Kaggle repository which includes Real World Data collected from various OTT Platforms with its IMDb rating and RottenTomatoes ratings. The OTTplatforms included here are Netflix, Hulu, Disney+ and Prime Video. We have created another dataset where data is collected from real world users about their favourite shows and perform clustering to procure more effective results. For this our group circulated a google form among all our contacts from which 120 people have filled this form giving details about their favourite TV shows, Ratings, Number of seasons and genre.

Fig.1 Snapshot of responses of the questionnaire

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Clustering Method

In machine learning[10], clustering is the process by which we create groups in a data,in such a way that objects falling into one group exhibit similar properties with each other and are different from all other objects that fall in other groups that have been created during the procedure.

Clustering algorithm divides the variables or cases into different parts via the distance in order to shorten the within-groups distance and distinguish different group

There are different clustering methods for different demands and it mainly depends on specific indicators, ultimate goal, data types etc. to adopt which one we can use. The different categories of clustering [9-11] is shown in Table I. This paper mainly applies clustering method to age grouping, ratings groups or on [no.of](#) seasons, learns and observes from then and uses the following techniques:

1. Hierarchical clustering
2. Agglomerative clustering
3. DBSCAN clustering

B. Hierarchical clustering

Hierarchical clustering is an unsupervised clustering algorithm which is used to find a relation and hidden patterns from the unlabeled dataset[12]. It develops the hierarchy of all the clusters and convert all the groups into a tree-shaped structure known as a dendrogram as shown in Fig.1

Fig.2 A Dendrogram based clustering

This clustering technique uses 2 different approaches to create clusters:

- 1) Agglomerative Clustering which is a bottom-up approach in which the algorithm starts with taking all data points a single clusters and starts merging them all until one cluster is left
- 2) Divisive is the opposite to the agglomerative algorithm that uses a top-bottom approach (it takes all data points of a single cluster and divides them until every data point becomes a new cluster).

A.1 AGGLOMERATIVE CLUSTERING

We will be using the first approach that is Agglomerative Clustering. This method starts combining the data points of the dataset that are the closest to each other and repeats this process until it merges all of the data points into a single cluster which contains the whole dataset or array[9].

Let us consider the steps taken for Agglomerative Hierarchical clustering algorithm:

1. The first step of the algorithm is to take every data point as a separate cluster. If there are N data points, there can be N clusters
2. The next step is to take the two farthest points (based on linkage) or clusters and merge them to form a bigger group. The total number of clusters reduces to $N-1$.
3. This algorithm will continue to merge the nearest points into a cluster until only one cluster is left.

We have performed the above steps of clustering on our first dataset and we have successfully obtained optimal clusters from the dendrogram created accordingly.

Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 below depicts the dendrogram and optimal cluster respectively.

Fig.3 Dendrogram for dataset 1

Fig 4 :Optimal cluster for dataset 1

Finally, according to the actual needs of the ratings grouping, have some categories combined or [split](#). On the basis of clustering results, we can analyze user features on a further step and develop a more personalized recommendation strategy.

B. DBSCAN CLUSTERING

DBSCAN is a density-based clustering algorithm whose main principle is to find the neighbors of those data points which exceed a certain density starting point. It also assumes all the clusters as dense regions which are separated by regions that have lower density points. Here, the ‘densely grouped’ data points are combined into one cluster. In this one can easily identify clusters in large datasets by observing the local density of data points.

A unique feature of DBSCAN clustering is that it can handle outliers way better than any other technique, due to which it finds an application in anomaly detection systems [11]. Also this method of clustering is normally used for recommendation systems which makes it a preferred one over others.

Some of the prerequisites of DBSCAN Clustering Algorithm are:

- Epsilon Value (eps) which is the radius of the circle around a data point and all other data points that fall inside the circle are considered as neighborhood points,
- Minimum Points (minPts) is the minimum number of data points that should be there in the region to define the cluster.

Based on the above parameters, we can classify the points as Core points or Border points or Outlier which are illustrated below in Fig. 5

Fig. 5 basic working

At last we can by performing DBSCAN Clustering on both our datasets we get a couple of clusters and on analysis of these clusters we can conclude on some results. On further analysis and comparison, the outcomes of both the clustering techniques combined we could derive better conclusions and have included those in the Results section.

VI: DATA VISUALIZATION

Tool used :Tableau [14]

Tableau is an end-to-end data analytics platform that helps many users to prepare, analyze, visualize and share your big data insights. Tableau is very good in self-service visual analysis which allows people to ask new questions of big data and easily share those insights across with any one within an organization or even outside.[14]

1) Dataset used:tv_shows.csv[13]

Fig6:Popular platforms according to age groups

Fig 6 shows popular platforms according to different age groups. In other words,the above image represents which age

Fig7: Maximum number of shows released in a particular year

Fig 7 shows the maximum number of shows released in a [particular year](#). We can see that in the year 2018 most of the shows were released.

Fig8: Shows available on different platforms(Netflix and Prime Video)

Fig 8 illustrates the shows available on Netflix and Prime Video platform. The light colored circle represents that the show is not available on Prime video and the darker one represents that it is present on Prime Video and if any circle is a little bigger and darker it represents that there are more than one row in our dataset where that show is present on Prime Video.

2) Dataset Used: TV shows form-responses.csv

Fig 9: Packed Bubbles depicting total number of seasons in a genre

Fig 9 depicts the total number of seasons in a genre. In the above figure we can see that in many genres like mythology,drama,thriller people usually prefer shows with more seasons.

VII. RESULTS

The outliers in the results for dataset1 include the shows that are rated really good on IMDb and bad on rotten tomatoes and vice-versa as shown in Fig. 10

For dataset2, the outliers are the shows watched by people in a similar age group (like20s) but no of seasons are very high like 50 as shown in Fig. 11

Fig10:AgglomerativeClusteringondataset1onthebasisof IMDb ratings and rotten tomatoes

Fig11:Agglomerativeclusteringondataset2onthebasisofa person's age and no of seasons they have watched.

We can predict the number of clusters formed on the basis of density through the Line plot of both datasets as shown in Fig 12 and Fig 13 respectively. On the basis of these clusters we further perform our analysis and draw conclusions.

Fig13 :DBSCAN clustering on dataset2 on the basis of age and no of seasons

Fig14:Maximum number of shows on an OTT platform released during a particular year.

In Fig 14 we can see a Line plot based on the maximum number of shows on an OTT platform released during a particular year.The blue line shows that on Netflix platform during the year 2018-19 maximum number of shows were released.

VIII. FUTUREWORK

In future work, we plan to use many other aggregation functions which would deliver flexibility and adaptability towards more relevant recommendations. Develop appropriate marketing strategies on the basis of preference clustering such as the program recommendation, platform selection and soon to achieve the conversion of data from information to something more useful. We can also use some supervised learning techniques like Classification etc and classify the dataset in various categories. One can also perform clustering on our dataset using various other techniques like Spectral Clustering, DBSCAN etc and on other columns like Genre (in the 2nd one) by performing label encoding on it or even the OTT platforms (1st dataset). It is also planned to identify user personality from choice of movies [14-16].

IX. CONCLUSION

From the results of our clustering analysis, we can conclude that for 1st dataset which were clustered on the basis of ratings on IMDb and rotten tomatoes gives us an insight into the preferences of a person and now with this data one can easily recommend shows to a person whenever they want to watch one.

In our 2nd dataset which was clustered on the basis of a person's age and the number of seasons of their favourite shows we can say that the majority of the people are interested in watching shows that have seasons ranging between 1-12 and very few people are actually interested in shows that have more than 12 seasons unless it is super interesting.

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